

QGameTheory: An R package for teaching quantum computing and quantum game theory to students

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4590990](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4590990)

Software

- [SORSE](#)
- [Event Website](#)

Category: posters

Published: February 19, 2021

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This is a package that has been written in the R programming language. As we know, R is an open-source software that is being widely used by statisticians and scientists all over the world. The purpose of this package is to build a very simple open-source project that will teach the basics of quantum computing and quantum game theory to interested students starting in this field. Available in the [CRAN repository](#), this package can be used to learn the basics to simulate the results of simple quantum circuits and also learn basics of quantum game theory models. Some of the models included in this package are quantum penny flip, quantum prisoner's dilemma, and more.

Links:

- [QGameTheory on GitHub](#)
- [CRAN repository](#)